

Isolation, characterization and biological potential of compounds from flowers of *Moringa oleifera*

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A phytochemical study of methanolic extract obtained from flowers of *Moringa oleifera* led to the isolation of seven compounds viz. methyl heptanoate, beta-sitosterone, 3,7,11,15-tetramethyl-2-headecen-1-ol, 24-methylene-9,19-cyclolanostan-3-ol and nonacosan-15-one, heneicosanoic acid and ethyl geranyl acetate. Characterization of these isolated compounds was done by using ¹H NMR, FT-IR, LC-MS and GC-MS. Different solvent fractions were also investigated for total phenolics content, total flavonoids content, total alkaloids content, minerals, DPPH free radical scavenging activity and antifungal activity. Correlation between various phytochemicals and antioxidant activity was also calculated at $p < 0.01$ significant level. A positive and significant correlation was found between phenols, flavonoids and DPPH free radical scavenging activity. The results of this study revealed that *Moringa oleifera* flowers can be explored as a potent source of antioxidants in nutritional food supplements. They also possessed promising antifungal activity against *Rhizoctonia solani* and *Fusarium oxysporum*.

Keywords: *Moringa oleifera*, chemical constituents, phenolics, minerals, alkaloids, antifungal activity.

Introduction

Agriculture is the largest sector in India which plays a significant role in socio-economic development but agricultural production is facing the destructive activities of various pests. So, synthetic pesticides are widely used for the control of these pests¹. But their continuous use had raised a number of ecological problems like environmental pollution, toxicity to humans and other organisms², left over residue, etc. There is a lot of hope that botanical pesticides will take us a long way in fighting the problems associated with these pesticides. The use of botanicals for the control of insect pests has recently advanced to a new stage. The recent frontier had moved to the study of natural plant products with broad spectrum of activity.

Moringa oleifera is one of the fourteen species of family Moringaceae which possess numerous biological activities like anti-inflammatory, immunodialatory, hypoglycemic, anti-cancer and antioxidant³. It is native to India, Africa, Arabia, South East Asia, South America and the Pacific and Carribean Islands⁴. It is known by a number of names like horseradish tree, drumstick tree, ben oil tree, Miracle tree and Mother's best friend⁵. It is a small to medium sized tree with straight

trunk and umbrella shaped crown^{6,7}. It produces creamy white, pleasantly scented flowers which are zygomorphic, pentamerous and are arranged in drooping panicles⁸. *Moringa* flowers are consumed either by frying in butter or by mixing with some other food as they are a rich source of potassium and calcium⁹. They are used in the folk remedies for tumors. They are also known to act as hypocholesterolemic and antiarthritic agents and helps to cure urinary problems and cold¹⁰. Flowers contain an antibiotic, pterygospermin, which is highly effective in the treatment of cholera¹¹. Thus, keeping all this in mind, it was thought of interest to investigate the flowers of *Moringa oleifera* for determination of its bioactive components as well as their efficacy for antifungal activity and its nutritional potential.

Results and discussion

Isolation and characterization of compounds:

Compound 1, (Methyl heptanoate): Compound 1 was eluted with pure hexane as viscous oily liquid (33 mg). Its R_f value was found to be 0.84 in benzene:hexane (3:7). The purity of the compound was checked on TLC plate as a single yellow spot on development with iodine. Its M^+ peak at 145

provides information regarding its molecular formula to be $C_8H_{16}O_2$. Absorption at 1735 cm^{-1} confirmed the presence of carbonyl group in the compound **1**. Other absorptions appeared at 2918, 2849, 1464, 1176 and 720 cm^{-1} are characteristic peaks of methylene and methyl groups. The $^1\text{H NMR}$ spectra of this compound in DMSO exhibited a triplet at δ 0.84 with coupling constant 7.0 Hz integrating for three protons of terminal methyl groups. Intense resonance related to eight protons of four methylene groups appeared at δ 1.25 as a multiplet. Another singlet appeared at δ 3.36 for three protons of methyl group alpha to carbonyl groups. The spectral analysis is in perfect agreement with the literature data of methyl heptanoate. From the literature survey, it seems that this is the first time report of isolation and characterization of methyl heptanoate from flowers of *Moringa oleifera*. It is used as a flavoring agent and is naturally present in many fruits like apples and plums¹². This might be possible that aroma of flowers of *Moringa* might be due to presence of methyl heptanoate in it.

Compound 2, (β -Sitosterone): Compound **2** was obtained on elution with benzene:hexane (1:19). Fractions 1–25 were repeatedly separated by silica gel column chromatography. The purity of the compound was confirmed by Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC). Its R_f value was found to be 0.24 in benzene:hexane (3:7), melting point $96\text{--}97^\circ\text{C}$ (literature m.p. $95\text{--}96^\circ\text{C}$)¹³. The compound responded to Liebermann-Burchard reaction which confirmed the presence of steroid. The absorptions at 2925, 2853 and 1723 cm^{-1} in its IR spectra confirmed the presence of $-\text{CH}_2$ and $>\text{C}=\text{O}$ groups. The molecular ion peak at m/z 409 in LC-MS deduced the molecular formula to be $C_{29}H_{48}O$. In $^1\text{H NMR}$ spectra of the compound in CDCl_3 , a multiplet at δ 0.86 indicated the presence of nine protons of three methyl groups at C_{18} , C_{26} and C_{27} . Twenty seven protons of three methyl groups (C_{19} , C_{21} and C_{29}), seven methylene groups (C_2 , C_7 , C_{12} , C_{15} , C_{22} , C_{23} and C_{28}) and four methine groups (C_9 , C_{14} , C_{17} and C_{24}) could be picked up as a broad signal in the range of 1.25–1.31. Two multiplets at δ 1.42 and δ 3.64 with coupling constant (J 4.0 Hz) integrating for three protons and one proton were assignable to two methylene (C_{11}), one methine (C_{20}) and one $=\text{CH}$ moiety. Methylene protons positioned at C_1 , C_6 , C_{12} , C_{15} and C_{16} appeared as a multiplet in the range of δ 1.50–2.00. The above data indicated the compound to be β -sitosterone. A complete agreement of the compound **2**

with the literature data of β -sitosterone¹⁴ established the identity of the compound to be β -sitosterone.

Compound 3, (3,7,11,15-Tetramethyl-2-hexadecen-1-ol): This compound was isolated on elution with benzene:hexane (1:14), 33 mg as viscous oily liquid. The purity of the compound was checked on TLC plate. Its R_f value was found to be 0.28 in benzene:hexane (3:7). Its molecular formula $C_{20}H_{40}O$ was deduced from its GC-MS. In IR spectra, absorption at 3410 cm^{-1} confirmed the presence of $-\text{OH}$ moiety. Other absorptions appeared at 2918, 2850, 1463, 1379 and 759 cm^{-1} . The $^1\text{H NMR}$ spectra of the compound in CDCl_3 exhibited a four methyl multiplet ranging between δ 0.89–0.94. Intense resonance related to overlapping methylene and methine units were found between δ 1.18 and δ 1.97. The resonance at δ 5.39 indicated the presence of double bond while a singlet at δ 4.58 indicated the presence of oxygenated methylene. A multiplet at δ 1.65 integrating for three protons with coupling constant J 12.0 Hz representing a methyl group at C_{20} position. Our data for the compound **3** is in perfect assignment of 3,7,11,15-tetramethyl-2-hexadecen-1-ol. It is the first report of isolation and characterization of this compound from *Moringa oleifera* flowers.

Compound 4, (24-Methylene-9,19-cyclolanostan-3-ol): It was obtained as colorless needles (49 mg) on elution with benzene:hexane (1:9), m.p. $120\text{--}122^\circ\text{C}$ (literature m.p. $122\text{--}123^\circ\text{C}$)¹⁵. It was recrystallised in benzene. Its R_f value was found to be 0.25 in benzene:hexane (1:1). Absorptions at 3419 and 3307 cm^{-1} indicated the presence of hydroxyl group. Other absorptions were at 2924, 2853, 1463, 1377, 1260, 1098, 1063, 801 and 720 cm^{-1} . M^+ peak in GC-MS at 440 provide information regarding molecular formula to be $C_{31}H_{52}O$. Seven methyl multiplets were identified between δ 0.94–1.19 at C_{18} , C_{21} , C_{26} , C_{27} , C_{30} , C_{31} and C_{32} positions. Protons at C_{19} appeared as a multiplet in the range of δ 0.65–0.67. A doublet peak with J 4 Hz appeared at δ 4.62 was assignable to protons attached to double bonds. A multiplet at δ 3.46 integrating for one proton was assignable to $-\text{OH}$ functionality. Another multiplet appearing from δ 1.36–1.66 with coupling constant J 8 Hz integrating for four protons of methylene groups. A complete agreement of the data of compound **4** was found with the literature data of 24-methylene-9,19-cyclolanostan-3-ol¹⁵. It is the first report of isolation and characterization of 24-methylene-9,19-cyclolanostan-3-ol from flowers of *M. oleifera*.

Compound 5, (Nonacosan-15-one): Compound 5 was obtained on elution with benzene:hexane (1:1), 55 mg having melting point 75–78°C. Its R_f value was found to be 0.28 in ethyl acetate:benzene (1:19). Its molecular formula $C_{29}H_{58}O$ was deduced from its LC-MS analysis. Absorption peak at 1704 cm^{-1} confirmed the presence of carbonyl groups in this compound. Other absorption peaks are present at 2917, 2849, 1463, 1297, 937 and 720 cm^{-1} . The $^1\text{H NMR}$ spectra of the compound 5 in CDCl_3 exhibited no signal in aromatic region indicating aliphatic nature of the compound. A triplet with coupling constant (J 8.0 Hz) at δ 2.36 integrating four protons could be due to methylenes positioned alpha to keto group. A multiplet at δ 1.61 which integrates for four protons was assignable to methylenes situated at beta position to keto group. A broad signal appeared at δ 1.25 representing forty four protons was attributable to twenty two methylenes. A triplet having J value 8 Hz could be picked up at δ 0.88, integrating for six protons of two terminal methyl groups. Thus, the compound 5 could be characterized as nonacosan-15-one. MS fragmentation pattern also tends further support to the proposed structure. A comparison of data of this compound with literature data for nonacosan-15-one confirmed that the compound could be nonacosan-15-one. This is the first report of isolation of nonacosan-15-one from *Moringa oleifera* flower.

Compound 6, (Heneicosanoic acid): It was obtained as white crystalline solid (34 mg). Its R_f value was found to be 0.53 in ethyl acetate:benzene (1:9). The melting point of the compound was 46–47°C (literature mp 48–50°C)¹⁶. The molecular formula $C_{21}H_{42}O_2$ was deduced from its LC-MS analysis. The absorptions at 3439 and 1721 cm^{-1} in its IR spectra confirmed the presence of -OH and $>\text{C}=\text{O}$ functionalities in its structure. In $^1\text{H NMR}$ spectra of the compound in CDCl_3 , a sharp triplet at δ 0.88 indicated the presence of terminal methyl group. A broad singlet appeared at δ 1.28 for methylene groups integrating for thirty-four protons. A multiplet was observed at δ 2.04 for methylene protons at C-3 position. The spectrum also exhibited a triplet at δ 2.32 for two protons alpha to carboxylic group. The above spectral data helped us to identify the compound 6 to be heneicosanoic acid. This is the first report of isolation and characterization of heneicosanoic acid from flowers of *Moringa oleifera*.

Compound 7, (Ethyl geranyl acetate): This compound was isolated on elution with ethyl acetate:benzene (1:14). The

purity of the compound was checked on TLC plate. Its R_f value was found to be 0.33 in ethyl acetate. Its molecular formula $C_{14}H_{24}O_2$ was deduced from its LC-MS. In IR spectra, absorption at 1731 cm^{-1} confirmed the presence of carbonyl moiety. The $^1\text{H NMR}$ spectra of the compound in DMSO exhibited a singlet of three protons at δ 0.88. The resonance at δ 1.24 indicated the presence of two methyl groups alpha to double bond. Two triplets at δ 1.98 and δ 2.26 integrating for four protons with coupling constant J 4 Hz represents the methylene protons of olefinic bond. Methine protons of olefinic bond resonate at δ 3.68 and δ 4.06 as singlet and quartet respectively. Intense resonance related to five protons of ethyl group was observed at δ 3.36 as multiplet. Thus, based on the above information, the compound 7 was identified as ethyl geranyl acetate. This is the first time report of isolation and characterization of ethyl geranyl acetate from flowers of *Moringa oleifera*.

Total phenolics content: Plant phenolics are the most abundant secondary metabolites possessing one or more aromatic rings with hydroxyl groups. These include phenolic acids, flavonoids, tannins, stilbenes and lignans¹⁷. They act as high level antioxidants because of their ability to scavenge free radicals and active oxygen species. Folin-Ciocalteu reagent method is based on the transfer of electrons from phenolic compounds to phosphomolybdic/phosphotungstic acid complexes in alkaline medium. This result in formation of blue colored complex¹⁸ whose intensity was determined spectrophotometrically at 725 nm. Total phenolics content of various extract/fractions of flowers of *Moringa oleifera* is expressed in terms of gallic acid equivalent (GAE) in Fig. 1. It was calculated using the following linear regression equation obtained from standard plot of gallic acid.

$$y = 0.0167x - 0.0095, R^2 = 0.999$$

where y is the absorbance and x is the amount of gallic acid in μg .

The results of the present study found that the total phenolics content was found to be maximum in acetone fraction of flowers of *M. oleifera* followed by ethyl acetate ($35.94 \pm 0.06\text{ mg GAE g}^{-1}$), hexane ($33.08 \pm 0.10\text{ mg GAE g}^{-1}$) and water ($31.54 \pm 0.20\text{ mg GAE g}^{-1}$) fractions. Methanol extract also contained moderate amount of total phenols i.e. $30.94 \pm 0.06\text{ mg GAE g}^{-1}$. Very low amount of total phenolics were found in benzene and chloroform fractions having value $3.68 \pm 0.13\text{ mg GAE g}^{-1}$ and $8.13 \pm 0.06\text{ mg GAE g}^{-1}$ respectively. Thus,

Fig. 1. Chemical structures of compounds isolated from flowers of *Moringa oleifera*.

it was found that there was a significant difference in the amount of total phenols in different solvent fractions/extract of flowers of *Moringa oleifera*. This difference might be attributed to the presence of different types of phenolic compounds (from very simple polyphenols to highly polymerized phenols) in the crude extract¹⁷. The recovery of these compounds in the extract depends not only on the nature of plant sample but also depends on the polarity of the solvent used¹⁹, extraction time and temperature²⁰. In general, methanol was found to be better solvent for extraction of low molecular weight phenols while acetone was found to be more efficient for high molecular weight phenols²¹. Our results depicted that acetone fraction contained maximum amount of phenols which lead to the conclusion that it may contain high molecular weight polyphenols in greater amounts and low molecular weight polyphenols in smaller amounts.

Total flavonoids content: Flavonoids are the most abundant polyphenols found in the plants. Chemically, they consist of two benzene rings joined by a heterocyclic pyran ring. They can be categorized into different classes like flavones, flavonones, flavonols, etc. which differ from one another in the substitution of pyran ring and level of oxidation²². Flavonoids which are present in food are responsible for color, taste, protection of vitamins and enzymes and prevention of oxidation of fats²³. Thus, the amount of total flavonoids in

different extract/fractions of flowers of *Moringa oleifera* were determined by using aluminium chloride colorimetric assay. It is based on the principle that aluminium chloride forms acid stable complexes with the C-4 keto group and either the C-3 or C-5 hydroxyl group of flavones and flavonols. It also forms acid labile complexes with the *o*-dihydroxyl groups in the benzene rings of flavonoids²⁴. Total flavonoids content is expressed in terms of catechin equivalent (CE) and is presented in Fig. 2. It was calculated by using the following linear regression equation obtained from the standard plot of catechin:

$$y = 0.0038x + 0.0019, R^2 = 0.9968$$

where y is the absorbance and x is the amount of catechin in μg .

The data presented in Fig. 2 revealed that total flavonoids content of flowers of drumstick tree was found to be highest in ethyl acetate fraction. It was followed by acetone fraction ($38.00 \pm 0.33 \text{ mg CE g}^{-1}$) and then methanol extract ($33.00 \pm 0.33 \text{ mg CE g}^{-1}$). Water and chloroform fraction of flowers contained moderate amount of total flavonoids having value 16.22 ± 0.19 and $17.22 \pm 0.51 \text{ mg CE g}^{-1}$ respectively. Hexane ($2.31 \pm 0.15 \text{ mg CE g}^{-1}$) and benzene ($1.11 \pm 0.19 \text{ mg CE g}^{-1}$) fractions contained very low amounts of total flavonoids. The flavonoids content of ethyl acetate and acetone fractions and methanol extract were found to

Fig. 2. Phytochemical composition of different extract fractions of *Moringa oleifera* flowers: All values are mean of three replicates. Total phenolics content is expressed in mg GAE g⁻¹ (milligrams of gallic acid equivalent per gram). Total flavonoids content is expressed in mg CE g⁻¹ (milligrams of catechin equivalent per gram). Total alkaloids content is expressed in mg BNE g⁻¹ (milligrams of bismuth nitrate equivalent per gram).

be higher which might be due to the presence of higher amounts of acylated and methylated form of phenols and flavonoids as well as its aglycone content. Flowers contained lower amount of total flavonoids in water fraction which also supports the above result as the methylated and acylated form of flavonoids are less soluble in water.

Total alkaloids content: Alkaloids are nitrogen containing organic compounds of plant origin. Most of the alkaloids have complex chemical structures of multiple ring systems. These compounds are known to possess many pharmacological properties. Therefore, it is decided to estimate the total alkaloids content of various solvent fractions of *Moringa oleifera* flowers. The alkaloids content was determined by using Dragendorff's reagent method in which alkaloids are precipitated as (BiI₃)(Alk·HI) by Dragendorff's reagent. Bismuth forms a yellow bismuth complex {Bi[CS(NH₂)₃]}(NO₃)₃ in nitric acid medium with thiourea whose intensity is measured at 435 nm. The bismuth from the alkaloidal complex is completely released by disodium sulfide²⁵. Total alkaloids content is expressed in terms of bismuth nitrate equivalent (BNE) in Fig. 2. The amount of total alkaloids was calculated using the following linear regression equation obtained from the standard plot of bismuth nitrate.

$$y = 0.0023x - 0.0136, R^2 = 0.9964$$

where y is the absorbance and x is the amount of bismuth nitrate in μg .

It is depicted from the data presented in Fig. 2 that metha-

nol extract of flowers of *M. oleifera* contained maximum amount of total alkaloids (323.17 \pm 0.76 mg BNE g⁻¹) while benzene fraction contained minimum amount of total alkaloids (72.83 \pm 0.76 mg BNE g⁻¹). Chloroform, ethyl acetate and water fractions contained moderate amount of total alkaloids with 115.33 \pm 0.76, 109.50 \pm 1.32 and 185.00 \pm 1.00 mg BNE g⁻¹ of total alkaloids respectively. Comparatively, low amount of alkaloids were found in hexane (74.00 \pm 0.50 mg BNE g⁻¹), benzene (72.83 \pm 0.76 mg BNE g⁻¹) and acetone (77.17 \pm 1.26 mg BNE g⁻¹) fractions. Thus, it can be seen that flowers of *Moringa oleifera* contained very high amounts of alkaloids. Traditionally, people used to boil them in water for 5–10 min prior to its use and then consume them after discarding the water. This might proved to be helpful in removing alkaloids.

Mineral content: Minerals are an important part of human diet as they serve as co-factors for many physiologic and metabolic functions. *Moringa oleifera* is a good source of various nutrients like proteins, amino acids and minerals. So, it is decided to estimate the mineral composition of various solvent fractions of flowers of *M. oleifera*. Flowers (Table 1) contained highest potassium content in methanol fraction (1449.00 \pm 0.01 mg/100 g) and lowest in chloroform fraction (20.10 \pm 0.01 mg/100 g). Iron and copper concentrations were lowest in hexane fraction i.e. 7.40 \pm 0.02 mg/100 g and 0.59 \pm 0.01 mg/100 g respectively. Iron concentration was maximum for chloroform fraction (13.86 \pm 0.03 mg/100 g) while

Table 1. Mineral content (mg/100 g) of various fractions of flowers of *Moringa oleifera*

Sr. No.	Extract/Fractions	Iron (Fe)	Copper (Cu)	Zinc (Zn)	Manganese (Mn)	Nitrogen (N)	Phosphorus (P)	Potassium (K)
1.	Hexane	7.40±0.02	0.59±0.01	134.40±0.34	0.23±0.00	1100.00±0.04	468.75±0.67	32.90±0.03
2.	Benzene	8.20±0.33	2.67±0.58	47.60±0.02	0.23±0.04	437.50±0.45	181.25±1.55	22.60±1.02
3.	Chloroform	13.86±0.03	2.42±0.04	72.30±0.03	0.25±0.00	350.00±0.02	225.00±0.33	20.10±0.01
4.	Ethyl acetate	12.85±0.05	11.93±0.04	167.50±0.67	0.31±0.01	662.50±0.33	262.50±0.33	22.60±0.02
5.	Acetone	9.91±0.56	3.72±0.02	394.10±0.04	0.61±0.00	1375.00±0.01	206.25±0.04	120.50±0.45
6.	Water	10.73±0.03	3.04±0.67	280.70±0.02	0.92±0.01	1212.50±0.88	368.75±0.34	1266.50±0.58
7.	Methanol	11.00±0.01	1.29±0.03	275.20±0.45	0.04±0.00	1325.00±0.04	468.75±0.67	1449.00±0.01
	SE(d)				0.202			
	CD at 5%				0.437			
	CV%				2.339			

Mineral content was expressed in mg/100 g. All values are mean ± standard deviation. Values are mean of three replicates (n=3).

copper concentration was maximum for ethyl acetate fraction (11.93±0.04 mg/100 g). Zinc concentration was ranging from 47.60±0.02 mg/100 g in benzene fraction to 394.10±0.04 mg/100 g in acetone fraction. Comparatively, manganese was present in very low concentrations. It varied from 0.23±0.00 mg/100 g (hexane and benzene fraction) to 0.92±0.01 mg/100 g (water fraction). Nitrogen content of drumstick tree flowers was found to be minimum in chloroform fraction (350.00±0.02 mg/100 g) and maximum in acetone fraction (1375.00±0.01 mg/100 g). Phosphorus content was ranging from 181.25±1.55 mg/100 g (benzene fraction) to 468.75±0.67 mg/100 g (hexane fraction and methanol extract). There was a significant difference in mineral content of various extract/fractions of flowers of *M. oleifera*. This might be due to the variable uptake of minerals by plant and differences in solvent efficacy to dissolve minerals. Flowers of *M. oleifera* are a good source of all the important minerals. So they can be used as a viable supplement and a source of dietary minerals in human food.

DPPH free radical scavenging activity: 2,2'-Diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl radical is one of the few stable and commercially available organic nitrogen radical (DPPH[•]) which is often used in evaluation of radical scavenging activity. It has a characteristic absorption maximum at 517 nm. The antioxidants present in plant extracts reacts with purple coloured DPPH and convert it into a colorless α,α -diphenyl- β -picryl hydrazine. Antioxidants either transfer an electron or hydrogen atom to DPPH and thus help in neutralizing its free radi-

cals. The degree of discoloration indicates the scavenging potential of the antioxidant extract²⁶. Mean percent free radical scavenging activity of various extract/fractions of flowers of drumstick tree are shown in Fig. 3 with their IC₅₀ values in Table 2. Hexane fraction was found to have maximum activity at 1000 µg/ml concentration i.e. 99.01±0.17%. Very good activity was shown by methanol extract with 98.41±0.14% antioxidant potential at 800 µg/ml concentration. It was followed by radical scavenging activity of acetone and water fractions with 96.65±0.24 and 96.81±0.14% activity at 1000 and 800 µg/ml concentrations respectively. Chloroform fraction of drumstick tree exhibited 40.85±0.75% antioxidant activity at 1000 µg/ml concentration. Minimum activity was possessed by benzene fraction i.e. 25.22±0.59% at highest tested concentration (1000 µg/ml). The radical scavenging activity in terms of their IC₅₀ values revealed the order as

Table 2. Antioxidant activity (IC₅₀ values) of various extract/fractions of flowers of *Moringa oleifera*

Sr. No.	Extract/Fractions	Regression equation	IC ₅₀ value (µg/ml)
1.	Hexane	$y = 9E-05x^2 + 0.1693x + 8.0565$	221.63
2.	Benzene	$y = 9E-06x^2 + 0.0076x + 8.3282$	1770.60
3.	Chloroform	$y = -1E-05x^2 + 0.0478x + 2.908$	1388.55
4.	Ethyl acetate	$y = -0.0001x^2 + 0.2429x - 4.3537$	249.37
5.	Acetone	$y = -0.0006x^2 + 0.5451x - 11.128$	131.04
6.	Water	$y = -5E-05x^2 + 0.202x + 7.4496$	222.95
7.	Methanol	$y = 0.0017x^2 - 0.1526x + 38.419$	138.83
8.	Standard BHA	$y = -0.008x^2 + 1.3156x + 33.976$	13.25

Fig. 3. DPPH free radical scavenging activity of various extract/fractions of flowers of *Moringa oleifera*.

acetone > methanol > hexane > water > ethyl acetate > chloroform > benzene. The differences in the antioxidant activity of different extract fractions might be attributed to differences in their chemical composition. Thus, all the fractions of flowers of *Moringa oleifera* have shown very good activity and can be used as potent antioxidants in food supplements.

The correlations between various parameters and antioxidant activity of different extract/fractions of flowers of *Moringa oleifera* have been analyzed and some of them are presented in Table 3. Correlation results depicted that there was a good correlation between total phenolics content, total flavonoids content and antioxidant activity. Phenolic groups

Table 3. Correlation between phenolics, flavonoids, alkaloids content and their antioxidant activity observed in hexane, benzene and chloroform fraction of flowers of *Moringa oleifera*

Phytochemical parameters	Total phenolics content	Total flavonoids content	Total alkaloids content	Antioxidant activity (IC ₅₀)
Hexane fraction				
Total phenolics content	1.000			
Total flavonoids content	0.743 ^{NS}	1.000		
Total alkaloids content	0.978 ^{NS}	0.866 ^{NS}	1.000	
Antioxidant activity (IC ₅₀)	0.978 ^{NS}	0.866 ^{NS}	1.000 ^b	1.000
Benzene fraction				
Total phenolics content	1.000			
Total flavonoids content	0.843 ^{NS}	1.000		
Total alkaloids content	0.989 ^a	0.756 ^{NS}	1.000	
Antioxidant activity (IC ₅₀)	0.999 ^a	0.866 ^{NS}	0.982 ^{NS}	1.000
Chloroform fraction				
Total phenolics content	1.000			
Total flavonoids content	0.990 ^a	1.000		
Total alkaloids content	0.989 ^a	1.000 ^b	1.000	
Antioxidant activity (IC ₅₀)	0.999 ^a	0.983 ^{NS}	0.982 ^{NS}	1.000

^aSignificant at 5% level. ^bSignificant at 1% level. NS- Non-significant.

play an important role in antioxidant activity^{27,28}. It has been reported that most natural anti-oxidative compounds often work synergistically with each other to produce a broad spectrum of anti-oxidative activities that create an effective defense system against free-radical attack²⁹. The composition of the extract is very complex; it consists of various classes of organic compounds which may exert opposite effects on the process of lipid oxidation. Based on the results obtained, it is highly possible that some constituents may be phenolics and flavonoids of different polarity extract/fractions may contribute to the antioxidant activity of the extract.

Antifungal activity: Antifungal activity of various extract/fractions of flowers of *Moringa oleifera* was estimated by poisoned food technique against *Rhizoctonia solani* (Fig. 4) and *Fusarium oxysporum* (Fig. 5). EC₅₀ values (μg/ml) of

different extract/fractions were presented in Fig. 6. A perusal of the antifungal activity data revealed that maximum activity was shown by methanolic extract at 2000 μg/ml concentration with 68.82±0.59% growth inhibition and 1195.56 μg/ml EC₅₀ value against *Rhizoctonia solani*. All the extract/fractions of flowers of *M. oleifera* were found to be more active against *R. solani* than *Fusarium oxysporum*. In terms of EC₅₀ value, ethyl acetate fraction was proved to be more active with EC₅₀ value 887.30 μg/ml and 1360.56 μg/ml against *R. solani* and *F. oxysporum* respectively. Out of all extract/fractions, benzene fraction exhibited minimum activity at 2000 μg/ml concentration with 29.80±0.34% growth inhibition against *F. oxysporum* while water fraction had shown minimum activity at 2000 μg/ml concentration with 38.82±0.59% growth inhibition against *R. solani*. Moderate activity was

Fig. 4. Antifungal activity of various extract/fractions of flowers of *Moringa oleifera* against *Rhizoctonia solani*.

Fig. 5. Antifungal activity of various extract/fractions of flowers of *Moringa oleifera* against *Fusarium oxysporum*.

Fig. 6. EC₅₀ values of different extract/fractions of flowers of *Moringa oleifera*: EC₅₀ means effective concentration at which 50% fungal growth was inhibited.

shown by hexane, benzene and chloroform fractions against both the tested fungi. However, all the concentrations were significantly different from one another. Irrespective of extract/fractions, 2000 µg/ml concentration was found to be the most toxic while 250 µg/ml concentration was found to be the least toxic. Critical difference values for antifungal activity of various extract/fractions of flowers of *Moringa oleifera* were calculated. Interaction of compounds and concentrations was statistically significant with a value 1.892 against *R. solani* and 0.744 against *F. oxysporum* for concentration × compound. This difference in antifungal activity of various extract/fractions of *Moringa oleifera* might be due to presence of different compounds in different extracts since different extract/fractions used in this study vary in terms of their polarity.

Thus, it can be concluded from this study that flowers of *Moringa oleifera* possess a number of phytochemicals and exhibit antioxidant and antifungal activity. Different solvent polarities had a great influence on the composition of the extracts. They are a rich source of phenols, flavonoids and minerals and hence can be explored as a viable source of these and as an antioxidant in different food supplements. However, further *in vivo* studies are needed for safety evaluation prior to its possible application in nutritional food supplements.

Materials and methods

Chemicals: Gallic acid, aluminium chloride, bismuth nitrate, disodium sulphide, butylated hydroxy anisole (BHA),

sodium hydroxide, sodium silicate, Neseller's reagent, 2,4-dinitrophenol (DNP), ammonium molybdate, ammonium vanadate and potassium iodide were purchased from CDH, Daryaganj, New Delhi, India. Folin-Ciocalteu reagent, thiourea, catechin and 1,1-diphenyl-2-picryl hydrazyl (DPPH) were obtained from Himedia Laboratories Pvt. Ltd., Nashik, Mumbai, India. All other chemicals and solvents used in the study were of analytical grade and purchased from CDH or SD Fine Chem. Limited, Mumbai, India.

Plant material: Flowers of *Moringa oleifera* were procured from campus of Chaudhary Charan Singh Haryana Agricultural University, Hisar, Haryana, India in the month of January. All the collected plant samples were washed thoroughly with water and shadow-dried for 10–15 days. These samples were then crushed with hands and stored in air tight containers for further use.

Preparation of extracts/fractions: Flowers of *Moringa oleifera* were extracted with hot methanol by refluxing method for 8 h. The process was repeated thrice and the respective extractives were pooled together. The obtained extractives were evaporated on a rotary evaporator to give a crude extract which was divided into two parts. One part was further fractionated into different solvents viz. hexane, benzene, chloroform, ethyl acetate, acetone and water. Each obtained fraction was evaporated to give a crude mass and stored in a refrigerator till use.

Column chromatography: The other part of the above obtained methanol extract was mixed with silica gel 60–120

Table 4. Correlation between phenolics, flavonoids, alkaloids content and their antioxidant activity observed in ethyl acetate, acetone and water fraction and methanol extract of flowers of *Moringa oleifera*

Phytochemical parameters	Total phenolics content	Total flavonoids content	Total alkaloids content	Antioxidant activity (IC ₅₀)
Ethyl acetate fraction				
Total phenolics content	1.000			
Total flavonoids content	1.000 ^b	1.000		
Total alkaloids content	0.945 ^{NS}	0.948 ^{NS}	1.000	
Antioxidant activity (IC ₅₀)	1.000 ^b	1.000 ^b	0.945 ^{NS}	1.000
Acetone fraction				
Total phenolics content	1.000			
Total flavonoids content	1.000 ^b	1.000		
Total alkaloids content	0.990 ^a	0.993 ^a	1.000	
Antioxidant activity (IC ₅₀)	1.000 ^b	1.000 ^b	0.993 ^a	1.000
Water fraction				
Total phenolics content	1.000			
Total flavonoids content	0.989 ^a	1.000		
Total alkaloids content	0.930 ^{NS}	0.866 ^{NS}	1.000	
Antioxidant activity (IC ₅₀)	0.930 ^{NS}	0.866 ^{NS}	1.000 ^b	1.000
Methanol extract				
Total phenolics content	1.000			
Total flavonoids content	0.866 ^{NS}	1.000		
Total alkaloids content	0.945 ^{NS}	0.982 ^{NS}	1.000	
Antioxidant activity (IC ₅₀)	0.866 ^{NS}	1.000 ^b	0.982 ^{NS}	1.000

^aSignificant at 5% level. ^bSignificant at 1% level. NS- Non-significant.

mesh size and subjected to column chromatography. A glass column of 1000×40 mm size was packed with slurry of silica gel (60–120 mesh size) in hexane. A portion of the methanolic extract of flowers was introduced onto the column and eluted with solvents of increasing polarity. The elutropic series of solvents used was hexane, benzene, ethyl acetate, methanol and their mixtures. Each eluate obtained was monitored by using Thin Layer Chromatography plates. The column chromatography afforded five compounds labeled as 1 to 5.

Identification of compounds: Melting points were determined with a Ganson Electrical Melting Point apparatus. IR spectra were recorded with a Perkin-Elmer spectrum RX-I FTIR. It has a resolution of 1 cm⁻¹ and scan range of 4000 to 250 cm⁻¹. ¹H NMR spectra of the isolated compounds were recorded on Sophisticated multinuclear FT NMR spectrophotometer model Avance-II (Bruker 400 MHz). CDCl₃ and DMSO were used as solvents. Chemical shifts were recorded in δ (ppm) using Tetramethyl silane (TMS) as an internal

standard. Coupling constants were determined by using the computer program and expressed in Hertz (Hz). LC-MS were recorded with a Waters Micromass Q-ToF Micro-Mass spectrometer. It is equipped with electrospray ionization (ESI) and atmospheric pressure chemical ionization (APCI) source having mass range of 4000 amu in quadrupole and 20000 amu in ToF. GC-MS of selected samples were recorded with Thermo Scientific TSQ 8000 Gas Chromatograph-Mass spectrometer having triple quadrupole and 2.1100 amu mass range.

Compound 1: ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO): δ 0.84 (t, 3, J 7.0 Hz, CH₃), 1.25 (m, 8, 4×CH₂), 3.36 (s, 3, CH₃-O-CO-); IR (KBr pellets) cm⁻¹: 2918(s), 2849(s), 1735(s), 1464(m), 1176(m), 720(w); LC-MS *m/z* (% intensity): 84(20.41), 106(100), 123(18.80), 145(24.57).

Compound 2: ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 0.86 (m, 9, J 4.0 Hz, 3×CH₃), 1.25–1.31 (br, 27, 3×CH₃, 7×CH₂ and 4×

CH), 1.42 (m, 3, J 4.0 Hz, CH₂ and CH), 1.50–2.00 (m, 10, 5×CH₂), 3.64 (m, 1, J 4.0 Hz, =CH); IR (KBr pellets) cm⁻¹: 2925(m), 2853(m), 1723(m), 1463(w), 1378(w), 1215(s); LC-MS m/z (% intensity): 124(3.55), 149(8.50), 202(35.10), 279 (9.83), 301(100), 316(9.13), 370(3.68), 375(7.76), 387(13.51), 409(31.53).

Compound 3: ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 0.89–0.94 (m, 12, J 12.0 Hz, 4×CH₃), 1.18–1.97 (m, 20, J 16.0 Hz, 10×CH₂), 1.51 (m, 1, J 8.0 Hz, >CH), 1.65 (m, 3, J 12.0 Hz, CH₃), 4.58 (s, 1, OH), 5.39 (m, 1, J 4.0 Hz, =CH); IR (KBr pellets) cm⁻¹: 3410(w), 2918(s), 2850(s), 1463(m), 1379(w), 759(m); GC-MS m/z (relative abundance): 43(100), 57(28), 95(19), 111(12), 123(27), 196(2), 222(12), 251(3), 278(2).

Compound 4: ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO): δ 0.65–0.67 (m, 2H, CH₂), 0.94–1.19 (m, 21, J 8.0 Hz, 7×CH₃), 1.36–1.66 (m, 4, J 8.0 Hz, 4×CH), 3.46 (m, 1, J 12.0 Hz, OH), 4.62 (d, 2, J 4.0 Hz, 2×CH); IR (KBr pellets) cm⁻¹: 3419(m), 3307(m), 2924(s), 2853(s), 1463(s), 1377(s), 1260(m), 1098(m), 1063(m), 801(m), 720(w); GC-MS m/z (relative abundance): 95.1(100), 107(85), 121(84), 147(76), 175(67), 187(41), 203(44), 216(43), 229(15), 245(9), 273(5), 285(8), 300(25), 379(27), 407(35), 422(20), 441(5).

Compound 5: ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 0.88 (t, 6, J 8.0 Hz, 2×CH₃), 1.25 (br, 44, 22×CH₂), 1.61 (m, 4, J 8.0 Hz, 2×CH₂CH₂CO), 2.36 (t, 4, J 8.0 Hz, 2×CH₂CO); IR (KBr pellets) cm⁻¹: 2917(s), 2849(s), 1704(s), 1463(m), 1297(m), 937(w), 720(m); LC-MS m/z (% intensity): 202(70.60), 243(9.86), 279(4.02), 301(25.59), 316(49.20), 387(45.23), 409(100), 425(10.55).

Compound 6: ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 0.88 (t, 3, J 8.0 Hz, 1×CH₃), 1.28 (br, 34, 17×CH₂), 2.04 (m, 2, 1×CH₂CH₂COOH), 2.32 (t, 2, CH₂COOH J 8Hz); IR (KBr pellets) cm⁻¹: 3439(s), 2918(m), 2850(m), 1721(s); LC-MS m/z (% intensity): 328(18), 319(37), 301(72), 297(12), 243(10), 202(15), 124(11).

Compound 7: ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO): δ 0.88 (s, 3, 1×C-CH₃), 1.24 (m, 6, J 8.0 Hz, 2×C-CH₃), 1.98 (t, 2, J 4.0 Hz, 1×C-CH₂), 2.26 (t, 2, J 4.0 Hz, 1×C-CH₂), 2.51 (s, 3, 1×OOCCH₃), 2.76 (s, 1, 1×CHCOO), 3.36 (m, 5, 1×COOC₂H₅), 3.68 (s, 1, 1×C-CH), 4.06 (q, 1, 1×C-CH); IR spectrum (KBr pellets) cm⁻¹: 2922(m), 2859(m), 1731(s); LC-MS m/z (% intensity): 226(3), 202(9), 191(26), 188(16), 180(7), 109(6), 107(100).

Determination of Total phenolics content (TPC): Folin-Ciocalteu method¹⁸ was used to determine the total phenolics content of various solvent fractions of *Moringa oleifera* flowers. Gallic acid (2.5–50 μ g/ml) was used as a reference standard for plotting calibration curve. 1 ml of each plant fraction (1 mg/ml) was mixed with 1 ml of 1 N Folin-Ciocalteu reagent and then added 1 ml saturated solution of 20% sodium carbonate. The final volume was made upto 10 ml using distilled water. The reaction mixture was kept in dark for color development at room temperature for 20 min. The absorbance was measured at a wavelength of 725 nm using UV-Visible spectrophotometer. The amount of total phenolics was determined by using linear regression equation obtained from the standard curve of gallic acid. The total phenolics content was calculated as mean \pm standard deviation (S.D.) and expressed as mg gallic acid equivalent (GAE)/g of dry extract.

Determination of Total flavonoids content (TFC): The TFC of various solvent fractions of flowers of *Moringa oleifera* was estimated by aluminium chloride colorimetric assay³⁰. Catechin was used as a reference standard to construct a calibration curve. Briefly, 10 mg of catechin was dissolved in 100 ml of distilled water and then diluted to give various concentrations of 2.5, 5, 10, 20, 40, 60, 80 and 100 μ g/ml. 1 ml of each fraction and standard catechin solutions were mixed separately with 4 ml of distilled water, 0.3 ml of 5% sodium nitrite and 0.3 ml of 10% aluminium chloride in a 10 ml volumetric flask. After 5 min, added 2 ml of 1 M sodium hydroxide solution and the final volume was made up to the mark with distilled water. The absorbance of the reaction mixture was measured at 510 nm on UV-Visible spectrophotometer against a blank containing all reagents except plant sample. The amount of flavonoids was calculated from linear regression equation obtained from calibration curve of catechin. The TFC was calculated as mean \pm S.D. and expressed as mg catechin equivalent (CE)/g of dry extract.

Determination of Total alkaloids content (TAC): The total alkaloids content was determined by spectrophotometric method of Dragendorff's reagent method³¹. 5 ml of each plant fraction was mixed with 1 ml of 0.1 N HCl and 2.5 ml of Dragendorff's reagent. The precipitates formed were centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 5 min. After centrifugation, the centrifugate was decanted completely and the precipitate was further washed with 2.5 ml of ethanol. The filtrate was dis-

carded and the residue was then treated with 2.5 ml of disodium sulfide. The brownish black precipitate formed was then centrifuged again at 3000 rpm for 5 min. The residue was dissolved in 2 ml of concentrated nitric acid and diluted to 10 ml in a standard volumetric flask with distilled water. 1 ml of this solution was taken and mixed with 5 ml of thiourea solution. The absorbance of this solution was measured at 435 nm against a blank containing 1 ml of nitric acid and 5 ml of thiourea. The standard curve was prepared by using 10, 20, 30, 40, 50, 60, 70, 80, 90 and 100 µg/ml of bismuth nitrate solution. The amount of total alkaloids was calculated from linear regression equation obtained from calibration plot of bismuth nitrate and expressed as mg bismuth nitrate equivalent (BNE)/g of dry extract.

Determination of mineral content: Minerals (Fe, Cu, Zn and Mn) were determined by using Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer. The samples were digested by wet oxidation. 0.5 g of each fraction was taken and 20 ml of diacid mixture (HNO₃:HClO₄ – 4:1) was added to each and kept overnight. Next day, the samples were digested on hot plate and the final volume was made up to 25 ml using distilled water. The readings were taken on AAS against a blank. The mineral content was determined by using the following formula and expressed as mg/100 g of the extract.

$$\text{Mineral content} = (\text{Abs}_{\text{Sample}} - \text{Abs}_{\text{Blank}}) \times \text{Dilution factor}$$

For nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium, the plant fractions were digested by following the same procedure but instead of HNO₃:HClO₄ – 4:1, 10 ml of H₂SO₄:HClO₄ – 4:1 diacid mixture is used. Nitrogen content was determined by colorimetric (Nessler's reagent) method³². 0.2 ml of each plant digest was taken in 25 ml volumetric flask and added 0.5 ml of 10% sodium hydroxide and 1 ml of 10% sodium silicate solution to it. For color development, 1 ml of Nessler's reagent was added to each flask and the final volume was made upto the mark. The absorbance of the samples was read at 440 nm using spectronic 20 UV-Visible spectrophotometer against a blank. The concentration of nitrogen was determined by using standard curve of ammonium sulphate and expressed in mg/100 g.

Phosphorus content was also determined by Vanadomolybdo-phosphoric yellow color method³³. 2 ml of plant digest was taken in a volumetric flask and added 1–2 drops of 2,4-dinitrophenol and then added ammonia solution till the development of yellow color. After color develop-

ment, added HCl dropwise till it became colorless and then added 5 ml of ammonium molybdate-vandate solution to each flask. Now make the final volume up to the mark and read the absorbance at 440 nm using UV-Visible spectrophotometer against a reagent blank. The phosphorus content (mg/100 g) was determined by using the standard plot of phosphorus chloride. Potassium content in acid digest of plant samples was determined by taking reading on Flame Photometer against a reagent blank. The concentration of potassium (mg/100 g) was determined by using the standard curve of KCl.

DPPH free radical scavenging activity: The free radical scavenging activity of different solvent fractions of *Moringa* flowers and standard butylated hydroxy anisole (BHA) was evaluated by using DPPH (2,2'-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl) method³⁴. 1 ml of each fraction and standard at different test concentrations was added to 2.5 ml of 0.1 mM DPPH solution taken in test tubes. The solution was mixed rapidly and allowed to stand in dark at 37°C for 30 min. The decrease in absorbance was measured at 517 nm using UV-Visible spectrophotometer against a blank prepared similarly without sample. The percentage antioxidant activity was calculated by using the equation:

$$\% \text{DPPH}^*_{\text{sc}} = \{(A_{\text{cont}} - A_{\text{samp}}) / A_{\text{cont}}\} \times 100$$

where A_{cont} is the absorbance of control and A_{samp} is the absorbance of sample.

The concentration of sample required to scavenge 50% of DPPH radical (IC₅₀) was also determined by using regression equation obtained by plotting the curve of percent inhibition with their respective concentrations.

Antifungal activity:

Test organism: The antifungal activity of different extracts/fractions of flowers of *Moringa oleifera* was investigated using two fungal species i.e. *Rhizoctonia solani* and *Fusarium oxysporum* which were obtained from the Department of Plant Pathology, College of Agriculture, Chaudhary Charan Singh Haryana Agricultural University, Hisar, Haryana, India. The fungal isolates were allowed to grow on Potato Dextrose Agar³⁵ (PDA) at 25±2°C until they sporulated. A 4–6 day old culture of each fungus was used for testing antifungal activity.

Bioassay: Poisoned Food Technique³⁶ was used for determination of antifungal activity of different solvent fractions and extract of *Moringa oleifera* flowers. Two sets were main-

tained – one for the treatment and another for control. The treatment set at different concentrations viz. 2000, 1000, 500 and 250 µg/ml was prepared by mixing the required quantity (200, 100, 50 and 25 mg respectively) in 1 ml of DMSO and then added pre-sterilized PDA. In control set, 1 ml DMSO was mixed with PDA. These treatments and control were then poured in pre-sterilized Petri plates and allowed to solidify at room temperature. After solidification, mycelia disc of 5 mm diameter cut out from 4–6 day old culture of test fungi were aseptically placed in Petri plates of different treatment and control sets. The Petri plates were then wrapped with para film along the rim to prevent contamination. The inoculated plates were then inverted and incubated at 25±2°C and the observations were recorded when the control plate got completely filled with test fungus. Colony diameter was determined by measuring the average radial growth of each plate. The data recorded in each case was mean of three replicates. The fungal growth inhibition (%) was calculated by using the following formula:

$$\% \text{ Inhibition} = \frac{C - T}{C} \times 100$$

where C = mycelia growth in control plate, T = mycelia growth in treated plate.

The concentration of plant extract/fractions producing 50% growth inhibition (EC₅₀) was calculated using SPSS Statistics 19 software.

Data analysis: All the experimental measurements were carried out in triplicate and results were presented as mean± standard deviation. One way and two way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was carried out to assess any significant differences between the means ($p < 0.05$) in Online Statistical Analysis (OPSTAT), CCS HAU, Hisar. EC₅₀ values of antifungal activity and IC₅₀ values of antioxidant activity were calculated using SPSS Statistics 19 software and regression analysis in Microsoft Excel respectively. All other measurements and calculations were carried out in Microsoft Excel 2007. To find out the relationship between various phytochemicals and antioxidant activity, correlation was calculated by using OPSTAT.

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